
MODEL PREPARATION TOOL BASED ON AUTOMATIC MACHINE LEARNING FRAMEWORK IMPLEMENTED AS A WEB APPLICATION

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Abstract

In modern days, plenty of data sources can bring additional information to their owners. However, not many of them can evaluate these sources because they lack knowledge in scientific domains such as statistics, mathematics, etc. Our paper aims to solve this kind of problem, and we created a tool that implements additional steps to ease this process. In our previous work, we implemented a data-cleansing utility. The second step is to choose the appropriate model according to the given data. In the first chapter, we describe the problem at an overall level; in the second chapter, we introduce the methodology used; the third chapter describes the project on its own and the obtained models; and the last one involves the conclusion.

Keywords

python, data science, automl, auto-sklearn, dataset

1 Introduction

In recent years, we have witnessed the rapid rise of new technologies and the upgrading of existing ones, and thus, a huge amount of data they generate. There are plenty of solutions available on the market, some of them for free and some of them are paid. This paper will not describe these applications because of the wide range, which is not our paper's aim. For example, more about free and paid solutions can be found at Mueller et al. 2019, Baumer et al. 2017, or Gearheart 2020. Those authors cover the two most used languages in data science (R and Python), and the last one covers a paid software solution called SAS. These three are very well known and used, but there are a lot of others like SPSS from IBM company and much more. Further in the text, we will introduce some of the most used technologies, but our main goal is to use Python with specialised libraries to create our application. Our goal was to create and implement such an application, where users with standard capabilities can upload his/her datasets and make all basic operations on them like data cleansing and first overall analysis of the dataset, consequently saving the dataset with processed modifications, model generation, and testing. First of all, the whole process of data science is to provide consistent data, but in real-world scenarios, this is impossible because of the possibility of duplicity, erroneous data, and abnormal or inconsistent data (Qinglei et al., 2017).

1.1 First steps in data science

As mentioned above, Qinglei et al. describe the process of preparing data for another evaluation. Without these important steps, the final result could be distorted; therefore, the decision could be wrong, and the whole process would be a waste of time. The first steps taken on the provided dataset should cover data deduplication, deleting erroneous ones, finding

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missing data, and correcting them by numbers with either neutral or average ones. There could also be other methods, but in our paper, we use three forms of replacing missing data: the first is providing zero values, the second average ones and the third is deleting whole rows of data because no other methods are suitable. The user can try all the methods independently to evaluate which method suits his/her needs. After processing all the data, we can choose the appropriate model to apply to our dataset. Choosing the proper one, we describe it later in our work.

1.2 R Language

R is a programming language and environment designed for statistical data analysis and graphical display. It is an implementation of the S programming language under a free license. Because it is free, R has already overtaken the commercial S in terms of users and has become the de facto standard in many areas of statistics. The functions of the R environment can be extended using libraries called packages. For version 3.6.2, there were 15,325 available in the CRAN central repository as of January 2020. An example of a frequently used package is ggplot2 for data visualisation. R is used from the command line, but several GUI frontends exist, such as RKWard, RStudio, and R Commander. R is also linked or used in commercial software, e.g., in the SPSS environment, users can directly write and run programs in the R language over open data.

R provides various statistical and graphical techniques, including linear and nonlinear modelling, classical statistical tests, time series analysis, clustering, and more. R is easily extensible with features and packages, and the R community is known for its active updates (Kaplan et al., 2017). Many standard R functions are written in the R language, making it easy for users to track algorithmic changes. The code can be linked to C, C++, and Fortran for computationally intensive tasks and called at runtime. Advanced users can use C, C++, Java, .NET, or Python to manipulate R objects directly. Another strength of R is static graphics, which can generate graphs suitable for scientific publications, including, for example, mathematical symbols. Dynamic and interactive graphics are available through additional packages (Lewin-Koh, 2015).

1.3 SAS application

SAS (formerly Statistical Analysis System) is an integrated system of software products the SAS Institute produces. It serves both as a database system in companies and as a tool for analysis and business use of data, and on the other hand, it is also used for statistical data analysis in science and technology. It is modular software, so the customer can use only the parts that suit him. SAS includes its programming language, also referred to as SAS. SAS software implements the whole lifecycle of analytics. It comprises data administration, which involves data cleansing and preparation. The second step is an analytic platform comprising various software tools and artificial intelligence; the last step is data quality management (Blokdyk, 2019). This platform is paid for and chosen by individuals not often, but it is widely spread in commercial areas.

1.4 Python language

Python is a dynamic, interpreted language. It is sometimes classified among the so-called scripting languages, but its possibilities are greater. Python was designed to allow the creation of large, full-fledged applications (including a graphical user interface see, for example, wxPython, which uses wxWidgets, or PySide and PyQt for Qt, or PyGTK for GTK+).

Python is a hybrid (or multi-paradigmatic) language; that is, it allows you to use not only an object-oriented paradigm when writing programs but also a procedural and, to a limited extent, a functional one, depending on what suits you or is best for the given task. Because of this, Python has excellent expressive capabilities. The program code is short and easy to read compared to other languages.

A distinctive feature of the Python language is productivity in terms of the speed of writing programs. This applies to both the simplest programs and very extensive applications. In the case of simple programs, this property is manifested mainly by the brevity of the notation. For large applications, productivity is supported by features that are used in large-scale programming, such as native support for namespaces, use of exceptions, standard tools for writing tests (unit testing), and more. High productivity is associated with the availability and ease of use of a wide range of library modules, enabling easy solutions to tasks from several areas (Jaworski et al., 2021).

Considering all the conditions that must be met, we decided to use Python language with all the packages provided, as the wide support of a community of developers, and the last fact was that this language is also widely spread in the commercial sphere.

1.5 *Streamlit package*

Streamlit is a free, open-source, all-python framework that enables data scientists to quickly build interactive dashboards and machine learning web apps with no front-end web development experience required. If you know Python, then you are all equipped to use *Streamlit* (Li, 2022). It is a cost-free product, consisting of all needed to build interactive web pages with charts, maps, sliders, and other useful tools. You can create dashboards and other interactive content with a few lines of code. It employs its web server, so the application is ready.

1.6 *Pandas and matplotlib packages*

In our application, we used, amongst others, a package called *Pandas* and *Matplotlib*. *Pandas* is an open-source Python package that provides several data analysis tools. The package has several data structures that can be used for various data manipulation tasks. It also has a variety of methods that can be used to analyse data, which is useful when working on data science and machine learning problems in Python. This package is widely used in data analysis and for working with external data like Excel worksheets, JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) files, CSV (comma-separated values) files, etc. Package contains extended capabilities for working with rows and columns altogether without having to use loops; functions are used instead, so we can call this type of programming paradigm functional programming. Python is a mix of procedural, object-oriented, and functional access, as has already been mentioned.

Matplotlib is a plotting library available for the Python programming language as part of NumPy, a numerical data processing resource. *Matplotlib* uses an object-oriented API to insert plots into Python applications (Nelli, 2018). In our application, it is used to display a histogram plot.

2 Methodology

Based on the literature review we have chosen the framework already mentioned in the text before. According to Richards, “Streamlit shortens the development time for the creation of data-focused web applications, allowing data scientists to create web app prototypes using Python in hours instead of days.” (Richards, 2021). According to Nokeri, “Secure web apps and

deploy them to cloud platforms” (Nokeri, 2021). We also decided to deploy our application into the cloud infrastructure in Oracle Cloud. Now, let us describe the steps to fulfil our goal.

- 1 We decided to develop an application that allows users to upload their data files and perform basic tasks to clean them up. This approach is called „data cleansing“, and according to Nauman „, Data cleansing is a complex set of tasks that takes as input one or more datasets and produces as output a single, clean data set“ (Nauman et al., 2022). This process takes a vast amount of time, so we decided to lessen this amount of time by reducing some tasks involved in data cleansing. After data cleansing, we will try to find an appropriate classification model applied to our dataset.
- 2 After some research, we decided to use web technology due to its widespread use and ease of use with web browsers.
- 3 Consequently, we decided to use the web framework *Streamlit* based on *Python* language technology.
- 4 Developing source code to implement applications.
- 5 Test and deploy on the local server.
- 6 Final application deploying on Oracle cloud infrastructure on Linux virtual machine.

3 Environment preparation

a. Prerequisites

We needed to take mandatory steps to achieve the final goal. First of all, we have to download Streamlit libraries from the home website of the project. The website has installers suitable for various operating systems and architectures. After choosing the appropriate one, follow the instructions to finish the installation process. To achieve this task, implementors should be aware of administering Windows, Linux, or MacOS operating systems. When the installation is successfully done, we can start the Streamlit framework. If everything works fine, we get a link and port on which the web server listens. The user is then redirected to the web browser, where the application will reside when completed. The steps described above are necessary to do otherwise, implementation will not be possible.

b. Choosing the appropriate dataset

Our application is now fully suitable for all datasets. We aimed usage of this application on datasets that mostly contain numerical values organised in rows and columns. So, we prefer a standard form of dataset known widely as Excel sheet or LibreOffice sheet but exported to CSV format. Other types of datasets that mostly contain string values are not suitable. We implement various encoders for categorical values, which will employ algorithms that convert categorical values to groups of numbers, allowing them to function properly. We used the sonar.csv dataset for this type of machine learning computations retrieved from GitHub to maintain a proper approach to our project. Dataset sonar.csv contains data describing whether echoed-back acoustic signals belong to mine (M) or rock (R) reflection patterns.

c. Choosing the appropriate model

Our project is divided into several parts: the first one is data cleansing and simple brief graphical analysis based on histogram plots, the second part is model selection, and the final part comprises model testing. Testing selected models will not be included in this paper.

Choosing the appropriate model is a very complex and difficult process, which comprises choosing the suitable type of estimator and appropriate algorithm, selecting hyperparameters and their values and also their different combinations, and so on. The machine learning industry is thus very complex to be understood by one person. When you look at machine learning algorithms, there is no unique solution or one approach that fits all. Several factors can affect your decision to choose a machine-learning algorithm (Harlalka, 2018). Machine learning is a method of data analysis that automates analytical model building. It is a branch of artificial intelligence based on the idea that systems can learn from data, identify patterns, and make decisions with minimal human intervention (Gradillas, 2021).

Our application is written as a web application with a very easy and intuitive interface, so any user with minimal knowledge of statistical methods or machine learning algorithms can use it for his data. We decided to implement classifier estimators only with prepared classifiers in the training dataset; this is called supervised learning; other types of learning we didn't use in our work are unsupervised learning and reinforcement learning.

For the complexity of such an application, we implemented a classification algorithm only, but the implementation of regression algorithms is planned for future implementation. Our application offers data cleansing, model search, and application of models found by automated machine learning. As depicted in Figure 1 user must provide the file in CSV (comma-separated values) with the pre-classified dataset to train the model on. Subsequently, the dataset is uploaded to the server, and searching for the model will start.

Figure 1: Model selection user's interface

Find best model

Choose a file:

Drag and drop file here
Limit 200MB per file

Browse files

sonar.csv 85.7KB

Find best model ensemble

Source: own elaboration

At this point, we must remember that this part is very sensitive because we have to choose the right amount of reasonable time to perform computations. We tested auto-selected models within a minute limit to testing because we trained models on small datasets, and we were limited by the hardware resource given to the server. This type of computation depends on the number of computer processors and the size of an operational memory. We tested our computations also on a notebook with eight cores and sixteen gigabytes of memory, but the server we used had one core and six GB of memory. Therefore, we have to choose parameters to avoid unreasonable time to get results. Our solution is prepared for server usage because of the web application type of service. We recommend using our application in a server environment with a minimum of four cores and eight gigabytes of memory to get reasonable

results in a reasonable timespan for larger datasets. We set the time to a fixed value (for us, it was five minutes); this time is the same for every hardware configuration, but here applies the clause that the more efficient the hardware, the more tested algorithms (figure 2 bolded text).

Figure 2: Finding the best model

```

auto-sklearn results:
  Dataset name: c1241e23-271b-11ee-80b0-00155de7a23f
  Metric: Accuracy
  Best validation score: 0.913043
  Number of target algorithm runs: 128
  Number of successful target algorithm runs: 113
  Number of crashed target algorithm runs: 14
  Number of target algorithms that exceeded the time limit: 1
  Number of target algorithms that exceeded the memory limit: 0

  Accuracy: 0.7391304347826086

  {66: {'model_id': 66, 'rank': 1, 'cost': 0.08695652173913049, 'ensemble_weight': 1.0,
'data_preprocessor':
<autosklearn.pipeline.components.data_preprocessing.DataPreprocessorChoice object at
0x7fc011c5eb80>, 'balancing': Balancing(random_state=1, strategy='weighting'),
'feature_preprocessor':
<autosklearn.pipeline.components.feature_preprocessing.FeaturePreprocessorChoice
object at 0x7fc0116867f0>, 'classifier':
<autosklearn.pipeline.components.classification.ClassifierChoice object at
0x7fc00e6c63a0>, 'sklearn_classifier': LinearSVC(C=493.6813394002163,
class_weight='balanced', dual=False,
  intercept_scaling=1.0, random_state=1, tol=0.05050518248614478)}}

```

Source: own elaboration

d. A brief look at the code

When the user wants to use the model auto-selection feature, he/she must upload the source CSV data file to the server. As the application's creators, we can tune model outcomes with so-called hyperparameters. This part of model creation is called hyperparameter tuning; only the application creators can now manipulate them. In future versions of the application, we can allow users to modify some parameters to a limited extent, like entering other times as we present in our application (five minutes). This should be carefully done because entering a higher value of the time limit can cause a massive workload to be applied to the server. Figure 3 shows a code snippet showing automated machine-learning Python code with hyperparameters in bolded font.

Figure 3: Python code snippet with parameters

```

X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.33, random_state=1)
model = AutoSklearnClassifier(time_left_for_this_task=5*60, per_run_time_limit=30,
n_jobs=8, ensemble_kwargs={'ensemble_size': 1})
model.fit(X_train, y_train)

```

Source: own elaboration

As shown in Figure 3, we are searching for the best classification model, and we can tune some arguments to achieve our goal. Beyond other possible parameters, we are using `time_left_for_this_task`, where we set the overall time to run the whole program; we can say the more time, the better the results. In our research, we chose a reasonable time to be set to five minutes because our dataset was not big enough to set a higher value. We performed tests with the newly generated model on the same dataset without classification labels. The generated model classified the same data as the original dataset with pre-labeled data rows. This can be considered as the best result to achieve. We would get a highly precise classification if we got a similar dataset. We have to consider that the final model could be overfitted if we strongly push for the highest accuracy of the model beyond a reasonable manner. Another parameter is `per_run_time_limit`, which limits the run time for one tested model, and we set it to thirty seconds, after which the cycle is terminated and another cycle with different parameters is used. The final parameter in our script is `ensemble_size`, which means several finally generated models ordered from the best to the worst. The figure below shows the three best models generated after we set the number to three.

From the given result (Fig. 4), we see the first three models ordered from the first `RandomForestClassifier` as the best one and the second and third `MLPClassifier` (Multi-layer Perceptron classifier) as the best models to use with our training dataset. The second and third places use the same classifier and, therefore, are distinguished by different arguments called hyperparameters enclosed in parenthesis that `AutoSklearnClassifier` chose as the best ones for our scenario.

Figure 4: Finding the best three models

auto-sklearn results:

Dataset name: fd2992cc-28db-11ee-804a-00155de7adf2

Metric: Accuracy

Best validation score: 0.913043

Number of target algorithm runs: 139

Number of successful target algorithm runs: 120

Number of crashed target algorithm runs: 18

Number of target algorithms that exceeded the time limit: 1

Number of target algorithms that exceeded the memory limit: 0

Accuracy: 0.782608695652174

```

{14: {'model_id': 14, 'rank': 1, 'cost': 0.15217391304347827, 'ensemble_weight':
0.3333333333333333, 'data_preprocessor':

```

```

<autosklearn.pipeline.components.data_preprocessing.DataPreprocessorChoice object at
0x7f5b4c0b9fa0>, 'balancing': Balancing(random_state=1), 'feature_preprocessor':
<autosklearn.pipeline.components.feature_preprocessing.FeaturePreprocessorChoice
object at 0x7f5b4be94700>, 'classifier':
<autosklearn.pipeline.components.classification.ClassifierChoice object at
0x7f5b4c0af970>, 'sklearn_classifier': RandomForestClassifier(criterion='entropy',
max_features=15, n_estimators=512,
                    n_jobs=1, random_state=1, warm_start=True)}, 53: {'model_id': 53,
'rank': 2, 'cost': 0.13043478260869568, 'ensemble_weight': 0.3333333333333333,
'data_preprocessor':
<autosklearn.pipeline.components.data_preprocessing.DataPreprocessorChoice object at
0x7f5b4bfbe730>, 'balancing': Balancing(random_state=1, strategy='weighting'),
'feature_preprocessor':
<autosklearn.pipeline.components.feature_preprocessing.FeaturePreprocessorChoice
object at 0x7f5aecffec70>, 'classifier':
<autosklearn.pipeline.components.classification.ClassifierChoice object at
0x7f5aecffe790>, 'sklearn_classifier': MLPClassifier(alpha=8.440979695014983e-05,
beta_1=0.999, beta_2=0.9,
                    hidden_layer_sizes=(157, 157, 157),
                    learning_rate_init=0.0002774746616573728, max_iter=128,
                    n_iter_no_change=32, random_state=1, validation_fraction=0.0,
                    verbose=0, warm_start=True)}, 79: {'model_id': 79, 'rank': 3, 'cost':
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<autosklearn.pipeline.components.data_preprocessing.DataPreprocessorChoice object at
0x7f5b4bfacc70>, 'balancing': Balancing(random_state=1, strategy='weighting'),
'feature_preprocessor':
<autosklearn.pipeline.components.feature_preprocessing.FeaturePreprocessorChoice
object at 0x7f5aed24d1c0>, 'classifier':
<autosklearn.pipeline.components.classification.ClassifierChoice object at
0x7f5aed44f700>, 'sklearn_classifier': MLPClassifier(activation='tanh',
alpha=2.89664380675713e-05, beta_1=0.999,
                    beta_2=0.9, hidden_layer_sizes=(50, 50, 50),
                    learning_rate_init=0.00019621972402090513, max_iter=256,
                    n_iter_no_change=32, random_state=1, validation_fraction=0.0,
                    verbose=0, warm_start=True)}}

```

Source: own elaboration

e. Retrieving final results

The web application returns the first best model in a brief information window and offers a button to download all the models with their hyperparameters ranked from one to the maximum models defined in the parameter `ensemble_size`. The web application generates a binary file in the background with serialised models used in the process of creating the best models. This data is subsequently deserialised and loaded into the application in the final step,

which consists of deploying the model on another dataset without knowing its classification hyperparameters used with the scikit-learn package.

4 Conclusion

Our paper aimed to allow people with less machine learning knowledge to ease the model preparation process. Our secondary goal was also to make an application that would be dataset-independent (meaning no special names for columns and rows), so anyone with any dataset saved in CSV format could upload the dataset to our server. These goals were fulfilled and there remains the third – much more difficult part to further process prepared (cleansed) data. In brief, these steps would comprise feature selection, various model testing, and finally, applying a winning model to our dataset. We've already implemented these steps in Python using the aut sklearn package specifically designed for these data science tasks. The final step in creating our application is to implement a possibility to test the generated model on the user's data by simply uploading them to the server, and subsequently, the saved model (generated model) will be applied to data using the Python library scikit-learn. After completing the task, they will be offered the file to download with classification results.

Resources

- Blokdyk, G. (2019). SAS Software a Complete Guide - 2019 Edition. Emereo Pty Limited.
- Gearheart, J. (2020). End-to-end data science with Sas: A hands-on programming guide. Sas Institute.
- Gradillas, R. (2021). Machine Learning Algorithms: How to Choose the Right Kind of Machine Learning Model. Independently Published.
- Harlalka, R. (2018). Choosing the Right Machine Learning Algorithm. Retrieved July 20, 2023, from <https://medium.com/hackernoon/choosing-the-right-machine-learning-algorithm-68126944ce1f>
- Jaworski, M., & Ziadé, T. (2021). Expert Python Programming: Master Python by learning the best coding practices and advanced programming concepts. Packt.
- Kaplan, D., & Horton, N. J. (2017). Modern Data Science with R. CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Lewin-koh, Nicholas. (2015). CRAN Task View: Graphic Displays & Dynamic Graphics & Graphic Devices & Visualization. cran.r-project.org.
- Li, S. (2022, January 14). Streamlit hands-on: From zero to your first awesome web app. Medium. Retrieved July 30, 2022, from <https://towardsdatascience.com/streamlit-hands-on-from-zero-to-your-first-awesome-web-app-2c28f9f4e214>
- Mueller, J. P., & Massaron, L. (2019). Python for data science for dummies. Wiley.
- Nauman, F., & Herschel, M. (2022). An introduction to duplicate detection. Springer Nature.
- Nelli, F. (2018). Python data analytics: With pandas, NumPy, and Matplotlib. Apress.

Nokeri, T. (2022). *Web App Development and Real-Time Web Analytics with Python: Develop and Integrate Machine Learning Algorithms into Web Apps*. Apress.

Richards, T. (2021). *Getting Started with Streamlit for Data Science: Create and deploy Streamlit web applications from scratch in Python*. Packt Publishing Ltd.

SPRINGER Verlag, SINGAPOR. (2018). *Data science: 4th International Conference of Pioneering Computer Scientists*.

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